

Not reinventing the wheel – Recommended websites

Many organizational websites are an excellent source of reports and other content relevant for women in STEMM academic leadership.

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28 November 2023, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10166125

We expect that many, if not most, of our readers are working scientists and engineers. We may all have experience with issues facing women in STEMM academics, but it's likely that few of us are experts in gender diversity in STEMM. Fortunately, there are abundant resources available on this topic. Organizational websites are a particularly good source for resources that are usually freely available. To make it easier to access these resources, we have compiled a list of relevant organizational websites.

[RESOURCE LIST](#)

We have also identified five websites that we find especially useful (listed in alphabetical order). Apologies for the bias toward the United States in these recommended websites – the full resource list includes European and other international resources.

[American Council on Education \(ACE\) Women's Network](#). This section of the ACE website focuses on women's leadership. In addition to valuable publications that can be downloaded, there are also blog posts and a link to join a learning circle.

<https://www.acenet.edu/Research-Insights/Pages/Diversity-Inclusion/Womens-Leadership.aspx>

[American Association of University Women](#). This site has much useful information/data about the gender pay gap and highlights 'news' related to women in academia primarily in the USA.

<https://www.aauw.org/>

[American Association for Women in Community College \(AAWCC\)](#). AAWCC provides education, career development, and advancement to women educators and students at community colleges.

<http://www.aawccnatl.org/>

Catalyst. Although not focusing only on STEMM, Catalyst contributes to building workplaces that work for women. This global nonprofit is supported by many of the world's most powerful CEOs and leading companies.

<https://www.catalyst.org/>

Committee on Women in Science, Engineering and Medicine (CWSEM). This is a cross-cutting committee of the U.S. National Academies of Science, Engineering, and Medicine (NAEM). CWSEM collects and disseminates data and information on the education and employment of women scientists, engineers, and health care professionals, and ways to increase the participation and advancement of women in all fields of science, engineering, and medicine.

<https://www.nationalacademies.org/cwsem/committee-on-women-in-science-engineering-and-medicine>

We imagine that these resource might be particularly useful when our readers are asked to take precious time away from their research and teaching to support diversity officers in identifying issues and designing procedures and processes to address them. A LOT of relevant work has ALREADY BEEN DONE and just needs to be adapted for specific settings in universities, research organizations, or STEMM industry. Please feel free to refer diversity officers to these resources. They can come back to us after they have done their homework. In the meantime, we can be busy with our research, teaching, and meaningful extracurricular activities.

In closing, here are a few questions to stimulate further thought, discussion, and action:

- Do you know of a relevant organizational website that could be included in the next version of the list linked to this post? If so, please write to us at: epistimiblog@gmail.com
- Have you benefited from resources provided by organizations?
- What are you doing (or could you do) to increase the benefits that women in STEMM academics derive from organizations (and their websites)?

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